

**THE CONTENT, ESSENCE, AND CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS
OF SOCIAL COOPERATION**

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ABSTRACT

This article comprehensively analyzes the content, essence, theoretical, and conceptual foundations of the concept of social cooperation. The factors contributing to the formation of social cooperation, its role in societal development, interpretations within various scientific approaches, and its transformation under modern conditions are scientifically examined. In addition, the main theoretical models explaining social cooperation and their interrelationships are analyzed

At all stages of societal development, interpersonal relations have occupied an important place. One of the most effective forms of these relations is manifested in social cooperation. In modern society, social cooperation is considered not only as a form of practical activity but also as a broad socio-philosophical category. From this perspective, studying its content, essence, and conceptual foundations has become highly relevant.

The history of political ideas created by humanity has evolved based on theoretical views about society and human beings, politics and the state, as well as the experience of societal development from primitive communities to the present day. At the same time, it becomes evident that modern society is the latest product of the civilizations created by humanity. One of the complex processes in the formation of civil society today is ensuring social compromise and agreements among people. In this regard, increasing the “guiding” and “implementing” forces in society through social cooperation is considered an important socio-political process. In particular, the problem of creating and ensuring an order based on social justice in civil society is currently connected with several factors that occupy a special place in the formation of social cooperation and its integral component — social partnership.

It should be emphasized that during the former authoritarian regime, the concept of “social cooperation” was interpreted one-sidedly and understood as “social agreement,” “social obligation,” or “social contract.” During the years of independence, however, people’s consciousness, thinking, and lifestyle changed completely. Their entrepreneurial spirit and attitudes toward the final results of labor have undergone radical transformations. Therefore, there is a need for a broad scientific analysis of the issue. In this context, the problem should be considered, on the one hand, from the perspective of globalization processes occurring worldwide, and on the other hand, from the standpoint of the specific features of modernization and economic liberalization being implemented in our country.

It is known that throughout human history, various conflicts and disagreements have arisen during the development of societies. Efforts and searches aimed at overcoming them have, in essence, been connected with issues of social cooperation. Naturally, views concerning social conflicts, their emergence in interpersonal relations and labor activities, as well as their causes and consequences, have always remained at the center of attention of thinkers from ancient times to the present day.

The Greek philosopher Socrates was one of the first thinkers in the history of political and legal thought to raise the issue of contractual relations between the state and free citizens. According to

Socrates' views, contractual relations between citizens and the state, particularly laws representing the interests of the homeland, should be placed above even parents; such laws serve as supreme parents, educators, and rulers for citizens [1].

It should also be noted that the idea of social cooperation, which later occupied a special place in the works of Eastern and particularly Central Asian thinkers, was developed in the views of Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Avicenna, Al-Biruni, and Alisher Navoi. Since a special place is devoted in our research to the teachings of Eastern thinkers on social cooperation, let us once again turn to the views of Western scholars.

One of the European thinkers, the Enlightenment philosopher Jean-Jacques Rousseau, substantiated the necessity of agreement for achieving mutual cooperation in social life within the framework of his concept of the "social contract." In his works *Discourse on the Sciences and Arts*, *Discourse on the Origin and Basis of Inequality Among Men*, *Julie, or the New Heloise*, and *The Social Contract*, he developed distinctive aspects of human freedom and democratization of society. According to Rousseau, during humanity's transition from the state of nature to society, inequality in property ownership intensified despite the declaration of equality before the law. Despotism, as in ancient Rome, relied on force and intimidation. However, "force does not create right"; on the contrary, citizens fully retain their right to oppose the government [2].

Rousseau justified this right of the people through his theory of the social contract: the contract is concluded not between the people and the government, but among all members of the nation. This contract is not a mere collection of individuals but a community of compatriots and patriots. The collective will is not a mechanical or arithmetic sum of individual wills but a general will expressing the common interests of true compatriots. This general will is always stable, unchangeable, and transparent [3]. It embodies indivisible and inseparable popular sovereignty, while the government exercises executive power in accordance with the will of the people. If it violates this will, the people have the right to remove it by force.

The social condition imposes a number of restrictions on members of society that were previously unknown. However, members of civil society simultaneously attain welfare and virtue. In the social state, instincts lacking responsibility are transformed into justice, while wild impulses become rights and duties. Even the limitation of freedom contributes to the development of spiritual capacities such as moral awareness and reason [4].

In general, Rousseau's theoretical views, especially his scientific heritage concerning popular sovereignty, made an important contribution to the development of theories related to civil society during his time. His research on moral norms and the establishment of society based on the social contract has not lost its significance even today in ensuring human freedom and rights.

The German philosopher Immanuel Kant was also an active supporter of compromise and concession in socio-economic relations. In his view, mutual benefit, compromise, and concessions occupy an important place in human relations and interactions.

As can be seen, social cooperation, as an idea uniting society, has always possessed a broader meaning than simple partnership. In the modern era, with the development of theories of the rule of law by thinkers such as John Locke and Rousseau, it became enriched by the concept of the social contract. Such agreements later acquired legal significance at the level of society as a whole. For example, the constitutions of the United States and several other countries clearly express the idea of social cooperation based on social agreement. Such comprehensive documents recognize not only relations between the state and society but also cooperation and agreement between society and citizens.

Turning now to the idea of social partnership, it historically emerged from the earliest stages of human life and was enriched with new values over centuries. Social partnership was essentially one manifestation of social cooperation in the twentieth century. In other words, social partnership reflected the contractual essence of capitalist society during the industrial stage of human development.

In general, there are two approaches to interpreting the concept of “social partnership”: narrow and broad. In our opinion, the term “social partnership” should be used in the broad sense, while “social partnership relations” should be applied in the narrow sense.

Specifically, social partnership is interpreted as social labor relations between the state and workers, entrepreneurs, population groups, or social groups. In this context, it focuses on relations between employers and hired workers.

In broad socio-political processes, concepts such as “interaction,” “harmony of relations,” “joint action,” “coordinated activity,” and “collective activity” are frequently encountered. These categorical concepts are objects of study in economics and sociology. Through these sciences, the specific features of social partnership related to different spheres of socio-political life are revealed. Problems related to healthcare, education, economics, labor, and social protection are also among the main subjects of researchers’ studies.

It is important to note that today representatives of the mass media and even some researchers often use the concepts “social cooperation” and “social partnership” as synonymous and equivalent notions.

Indeed, these concepts are interconnected and cannot exist independently of one another. However, there are important differences between them. As discussed above, they differ in scope and meaning. In our opinion, the relationship between these concepts may be compared to the relation between content and form, generality and particularity, whole and part. Here, the concept of “social cooperation” represents content, generality, and wholeness, whereas “social partnership” represents form, particularity, and part. In general, social cooperation is a universal method of collective activity, which is more effectively implemented through social partnership. Social partnership, in turn, encompasses relations within a particular sphere or sector of social life and creates conditions for the development of social cooperation.

The broader nature of social cooperation compared to social partnership is also reflected in Uzbek dictionaries. In the five-volume *Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language*, cooperation is defined as “being partners in activity, uniting, equally carrying out work, and acting in mutual interdependence” [5], whereas partnership is defined as “participation together in a particular activity” [6].

It should also be emphasized that the concepts of “social partnership” and “social partnership relations” should be distinguished from one another. Social partnership generally refers to bilateral or multilateral relations among social actors, institutions, and sectors, while social partnership relations mainly denote collective activities carried out within one sphere, such as labor relations.

Therefore, within the framework of our research, we use all three concepts — “social cooperation,” “social partnership,” and “social partnership relations” — in their appropriate contexts. If human beings are considered the core of social relations, then interpersonal relations within the framework of our topic evolve from simple to complex forms: “partnership – partnership relations – cooperation.”

Thus, social cooperation may be defined as follows:

Social cooperation is closely connected with the strategic goals, developmental ideas, and objectives of society and represents the collective activity carried out by the population and social groups across the entire society in the interests of national development and the realization of the country’s fundamental interests.

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